

Impact of Blood in Urine on Milk Likening

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ABSTRACT

The impact of blood in urine is more significant on milk likening both in males and females. The objective of the present study was to show a relationship between milk likeliness and blood in urine. Sometimes kidneys allow blood cells leakage into urine. Various problems are involved in causing this leakage like urinary tract infections. If bacteria enter in your body they cause infection and multiply in bladder is wonderful and energetic. Milk is a wonderful and energetic diet. It is used in different milky products.

Keywords: Blood in urine; Milk; Urinary tract infections.

1. INTRODUCTION

Sometimes kidneys allow blood cells leak into urine. The impact of blood in urine is more significant on milk likening both in males and females. Various problems are involved in causing this leakage like urinary tract infections. If bacteria enter in your body they cause infection and multiply in bladder. Certain other factors are also involved in leakage of blood such as aspirin and penicillin. They allow blood to leak into urine. Its symptom is burning and pain during urination's. Kidney stones and urinary infections also cause blood leakage. Certain tests are required to check the availability of diseases in urethra.

Milk is wonderful and energetic. It is used in different milky products. It can be used on industrial level for the production of many food products. It is used in cakes production. Cakes are used in different birthday parties. Sweets are also produced from milk. It is strong diet for the teetees and bones.

The objective of the present study was to show a relationship between milk likeliness and blood in urine.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A urine test strip was used for this purpose. It was used to check the changes in urine analysis. First of all took urine samples and dip in the urine strip. Results were appeared. In this way various changes in urine or presence of blood can be checked.

3. STUDY OBJECTIVE

A simple scheme is designed to show a relationship between milk likeliness and blood in urine.

Statistical Analysis - MS Office is used for this purpose.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Urine test was performed to check the various changes in urine analysis and presence of blood in urine. Hundreds students were involved in this work. Some people had positive results and some people had negative results. They had different tastes for milk likeliness according to their urine reports. Males and females also had different choices.

Table 1

Gender	Milk likeliness	Milk dis-likeliness
Male	90.90%	9.09%
Female	90%	10%

Males had more attraction towards milk than females.

5. CONCLUSION

The people with positive sign show attraction towards milk as compared to the negative signs. It also concluded that males had more attraction towards milk than females.

Declarations

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Competing Interests Statement

The authors declare no competing financial, professional, or personal interests.

Consent for publication

The authors declare that they consented to the publication of this research work.

Authors' Contributions

All authors equally contributed to research and paper drafting.

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